

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Some restorers and maintainers of WA cyto-sterile lines

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Using Chinese CMS line V20A as a common female parent, eight crosses with standard rice cultivars were made during 1984 wet season. To identify restorers and maintainers, 20 plants from each hybrid and the male parents

grown in the test cross nursery in 1985 were examined for pollen fertility and spikelet seed-setting percentage. Male parents of the F₁ that showed 70-80% pollen fertility and above 80% spikelet fertility were designated restorers. Male parents of the F₁ showing 5-7% pollen fertility were designated maintainers. Male parents showing intermediate pollen and spikelet fertility were designated partial restorers.

IR54, BIET8549, BIET1009, and Radha were identified as restorers, Br. 9 and Cuttack Basmati as partial

Spikelet and pollen fertility percentages in F₁ hybrids and their male parents.

Cross and male parent	Spikelet fertility (%)	Pollen fertility (%)
V20A/IR54	85.8	76
IR54	86.9	80
V20A/Br. 34	12.2	7
Br. 34	89.1	79
V20A/Br. 9	29.0	16
Br. 9	83.0	76
V20A/Cuttack Basmati	39.0	23
Cuttack Basmati	91.2	88
V20A/BIET8549	82.5	71
BIET8549	89.1	74
V20A/BIET1009	86.8	81
BIET1009	89.2	81
V20A/Radha	84.9	76
Radha	91.0	89
V20A/BIET8550	10.5	6
BIET8550	85.5	76

restorers, and Br. 34 and BIET8550 as maintainers (see table). □

Breeding methods

Rice dwarf mutant of Seratus Malam variety

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Seeds of Seratus Malam, a local upland rice variety (tall with long panicles and high yielding potential) were irradiated

Agronomic characters of dwarf mutant M-362 and the mother variety Seratus Malam.

Characteristic	Mutant M-362	Seratus Malam
Plant height (cm)	58.50	119.00
Productive tillers (no.)	4.50	10.00
Panicle length (cm)	17.17	27.00
Culm length (cm)	41.33	92.00
1,000-grain weight (g)	12.75	22.24
Yield per plant (g)	10.55	18.41

with gamma rays at 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 kGy in 1983. Plants were selected in the M₂ generation for dwarf and semidwarf stature.

From 50,000 M₂ plants, 130 semidwarf mutants and 1 dwarf mutant were selected. Dwarf mutant M-362 was isolated from the 0.1 kGy gamma ray treatment. It has significantly shorter plants, shorter culms, lower number of productive tillers, shorter panicles, and lower 1,000-grain weight than Seratus Malam (see table).

In the allelic test, dwarf mutant M-362 was crossed with Acc. 123 (carrying DGWG gene). Dwarf mutant M-362 was not allelic with Acc. 123.

Performance of dwarf mutant M-362 is shown in the figure. □

Stature of M-362 dwarf mutant and the mother variety Seratus Malam. Jakarta, Indonesia.

Seratus Malam

Dwarf mutant

Effects of antimetabolites on growth and differentiation of rice tissues grown *in vitro*

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We studied the effects of three antimetabolite agents — chloral hydrate,